

FINAL REPORT

1 General Information

DFG reference number: FR 4404/1-1

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Project title: **Making the direct link between light regime and forest biodiversity – a 3D spatially explicit modelling approach based on TLS, CNNs and ray tracing.**

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2 Summary

English summary

Forests play a critical role in maintaining biodiversity and ecosystem services, but understanding their complex spatial and temporal structures remains a challenge. Light distribution, a key abiotic factor, influences ecological processes, making its accurate modelling essential for habitat characterization and forest growth simulations. The project aimed to model light distribution in forest ecosystems by leveraging advanced 3D modelling techniques, including terrestrial LiDAR scanning (TLS), convolutional neural networks (CNNs), and ray tracing.

This required various methodological innovations. The project was successful in developing a full pipeline from a LiDAR scanning point cloud to a forest mesh model with spectral properties assigned to each element. Therefore, we implemented a segmentation of single trees, the classification to leaf and wood points, the classification of a species for every tree and the reconstruction of a mesh geometry. Leaf and wood spectra were generated using the TRY trait database and literature values. These mesh models and spectra can be directly utilized to run radiative transfer models.

Within this pipeline the deep learning-based species classification developed within the project yielded an overall accuracy of 0.79 (F1 score 0.79) in the classification of 33 species. A test of the whole pipeline on a solitary tree showed very high correlations ($r = 0.92$) with ground truth data of measurement values of 60 photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) sensors.

Additionally, various methodological improvements could be achieved for ground truth validation. A mobile PAR sensor system incorporating a precise positioning system has been developed and we conducted a study on the sensor fusion of thermal imaging and terrestrial laser scanning. The latter showed a significant relationship of surface temperature gradients along the tree stems and sap flow measurements on the same tree.

German summary

Wälder spielen eine entscheidende Rolle bei der Erhaltung der biologischen Vielfalt und der Ökosystemleistungen, doch das Verständnis ihrer komplexen räumlichen und zeitlichen Strukturen bleibt eine Herausforderung. Die Lichtverteilung, ein wichtiger abiotischer Faktor, beeinflusst ökologische Prozesse, weshalb ihre genaue Modellierung für die Charakterisierung von Lebensräumen und die Simulation des Waldwachstums unerlässlich ist. Das Projekt zielte darauf ab, die Lichtverteilung in Waldökosystemen zu modellieren, indem fortschrittliche 3D-Modellierungstechniken wie terrestrische LiDAR-Scans (TLS), neuronale Faltungsnetzwerke (CNNs) und Raytracing eingesetzt wurden.

Dies erforderte verschiedene methodische Innovationen. Im Rahmen des Projekts wurde eine vollständige Pipeline von einer LiDAR-Punktwolke zu einem Waldnetzmodell entwickelt, wobei jedem Element spektrale Eigenschaften zugewiesen wurden. Dazu wurde eine Segmentierung von Einzelbäumen, die Klassifizierung in Blatt- und Holzpunkte, die Klassifizierung einer Baumart für jeden Baum und die Rekonstruktion einer Mesh-Geometrie durchgeführt. Die optischen Spektren der Blätter und des Holzes wurden mit Hilfe der TRY-Datenbank und Literaturwerten erstellt. Diese Netzmodelle und Spektren können direkt für die Durchführung von Strahlungstransfermodellen verwendet werden.

Die im Rahmen des Projekts entwickelte Deep-Learning-basierte Artenklassifizierung ergab eine Gesamtgenauigkeit von 0,79 (F1-Score 0,79) bei der Klassifizierung von 33 Arten. Ein Test der gesamten Pipeline an einem Solitärbaum zeigte sehr hohe Korrelationen ($r = 0,92$) mit den Bodenwahrheitsdaten der Messwerte von 60 Sensoren für photosynthetisch aktive Strahlung (PAR).

Zusätzlich konnten verschiedene methodische Verbesserungen für die Validierung der Bodenwahrheit erzielt werden. Es wurde ein mobiles PAR-Sensorsystem mit einem präzisen Positionierungssystem entwickelt, und wir führten eine Studie über die Sensorfusion von Wärmebildaufnahmen und terrestrischem Laserscanning durch. Letzteres zeigte einen signifikanten Zusammenhang zwischen Oberflächentemperaturgradienten entlang der Baumstämme und Safflussmessungen am selben Baum.

3 Progress Report

The importance of forest ecosystems for various ecosystem services and biodiversity protection has been widely recognised and accepted (Gutsch et al., 2018). Despite decades of intensive research into forest ecosystems, our understanding of forest processes is still limited. One of the main reasons for this knowledge gap is our limited ability to fully capture forests in their complex spatial and temporal structure (Fassnacht et al., 2023). A key abiotic factor in a forest ecosystem is the distribution of light in the stand, which interacts with the plant material through the canopy. The modelling of light extinction is therefore a prerequisite for the ecological characterization of habitats and for a plausible simulation of forest growth with ecophysiological process models (Calders et al., 2018; Forrester et al., 2019; Kükenbrink et al., 2021; Lintunen et al., 2013; McDowell et al., 2020; Van der Zande et al., 2011).

Forest research has made tremendous leaps forward during the last decades in the spatio-temporal characterisation of forest due to various technological advances. First of all, Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) technology has paved the way to generate detailed 3D structural models of forest stands with reasonable effort (Coops et al., 2021). Second, machine learning toolkits, like deep learning technology, have developed which make it feasible to handle such datasets (Kattenborn et al., 2021). Third, models to describe the radiative transfer through the canopy increased significantly in performance and detail (Gastellu-Etchegorry et al., 2012; Qi et al., 2019).

Never the less, there has been various relevant obstacles to model light interception through a forest canopy based on LiDAR data when we started the project. A reliable and transferable method to classify the different compartments and materials (like ground, leaves, wood, tree individuals) of a forest scan were lacking, but these are essential to know since the different materials have very different optical properties. Tree species classification on LiDAR data was also in its infancy and there was no sufficiently reliable method to classify the diverse species set of a temperate forest. Since LiDAR data is just a large set of 3D points without extent or semantics, an additional method is needed to assign a planar or volumetric geometry to this data (Risse et al., 2018). Lastly, an efficient way is required to determine the spectral properties of the different materials and to translate the data into the right format for a radiative transfer model. Since our capabilities of measuring light in forest is limited to point measurements based on single expensive sensors, an innovative validation strategy needs be developed.

The work programme we have implemented followed these challenges with work package (WP) one data collection, WP2 CNN based classification, WP3 ray tracing model and WP4 ecological relevance.

The workplan, developed in January 2020 envisioned to start the project with extensive fieldwork and data collection. When the project actually started in February 2021 the reality of the COVID pandemic required a restructuring of the workplan and we decided to focus on the methodological advancements from WP2 based on existing data first.

Single tree segmentation and species classification

Since there was not sufficient training data available to train a deep learning model for single tree segmentation our first development was an improved version of a parametric single tree

segmentation. This should have served as a presegmentation for a manual postprocessing to generate the training data for a deep learning-based segmentation and a deep learning model to estimate tree species from point clouds of single trees. This parametric segmentation is now available as an R-package under open-source license (Frey & Schindler, 2024b; Murtiyoso et al., 2024). Our main improvements over existing solutions were an optimized cost function to assign points to the most likely tree base position, improved scalability due to the option of tiled processing and a very high computational performance. Meanwhile the publication of the 'Forest Structural Complexity Tool' solved the problem of single tree segmentation and leaf wood segmentation (Krisanski et al., 2021). We therefore shifted our focus towards the tree species classification.

We followed two approaches to complete this task the first one is directly based on LiDAR point clouds, while the second one is a sensor fusion approach based on RGB camera images taken in tandem with the LiDAR scan. For the point cloud based approach we joined an endeavour within the COST action [3DforEcoTec](#) where we utilized our scanning and segmentation pipeline to contribute 750 trees to a common dataset with more than 20,000 single tree point clouds of more than 30 species (Puliti, Lines, Müllerová, Frey, Schindler, Straker, Allen, Lukas, et al., 2024). We developed a deep learning pipeline (Frey & Schindler, 2024c) for the data science competition in the framework of the COST action. Our model achieved the best performance of all the submissions. The publication is currently under review in 'Methods in Ecology and Evolution' and is available as a preprint (Puliti, Lines, Müllerová, Frey, Schindler, Straker, Allen, Winiwarter, et al., 2024). The model weights are available as published data (Frey & Schindler, 2024a).

The second approach was to detect the stems on the RGB-pictures the LiDAR scanner takes during his scans and to determine the species on such photographs. The species information can be projected afterwards onto the LiDAR point cloud. This procedure has multiple advantages over the method based on the point cloud data directly. Image based species recognition is far more advanced than the one based on point clouds and average accuracies reached are usually higher. The spectral and spatial resolution of the images is higher than that of the scanner, which gives the classifier more information, although the depth information is missing. More training data is publicly available and the generation of training data is less time consuming, due to the fact that the 3D segmentation is not necessary and there is no error propagation from the segmentation to the classification. Since public datasets were only to a limited use for us we generated an additional trainings dataset of 8,700 images with labels of 23 species or species groups. We used a modified version of the YOLO8 deep learning model to train an instance segmentation model. This was extremely successful in predicting species masks on tree stems with an F1 score of 0.90 (see Figure 1 for examples).

Even though we optimized the pipeline to clip sections from the scanners images resembling the training data and we did extensive tests with image augmentation techniques, the model performed only moderate on the scanning images mostly due to difficult lighting conditions and occlusion (F1 score 0.49). This score was also partly influenced by problems with the test data (incomplete labels). This problem might be overcome by the inclusion of citizen science data in the future offering a greater variability in recording conditions and spatial extend (Soltani et al., 2024).

Figure 1: Example of image based segmentation labels for stems of different species left and predictions of our model right.

Geometry reconstruction

With the species classification all necessary classification tasks for the project were accomplished, but to run a radiative transfer model we still need to generate a polygon geometry for the vegetation. We developed a software pipeline which directly takes a leaf-on scan as an input and generates a mesh as an output. By fitting a small plane into voxels based on the point cloud (Figure 2). The algorithm has been highly computationally optimized and published under an open source license (<https://github.com/JulFrey/dotshadow>, Frey & Kröner, 2024). We conducted a validation of the approach based on the shadow cast by an agroforestry tree (*Malus domestica*). We measured the light intercepted based on a grid of 60 photosynthetic active radiation (PAR) sensors on the ground. The shadow of the tree was modelled utilizing our pipeline and the LESS radiative transfer model (Qi et al., 2019). We compared our validation result with an alternative approach using turbid media voxels instead of the polygon reconstruction. Our approach yielded very high correlations with the ground truth PAR sensor data ($r = 0.92$) which was noticeable more precise than the turbid voxel approach ($r = 0.85$) (Frey et al., under review).

Radiative transfer modelling and ground truth validation

Besides the methodological challenges in point cloud processing we had to tackle various challenges in the ground truth validation for the project. It was envisioned to have a spatial explicit measurement of the incident radiation based on thermal imaging LiDAR sensor fusion in the proposal. This is implemented by mounting and calibrating a thermal imager (Infratec Head HD910) on our terrestrial LiDAR (VZ400i, RIEGL Laser Measurement Systems GmbH, Horn, Austria). The scanner captures a series of thermal images right after the LiDAR scan is conducted and the temperature information can be projected to the point cloud. The result is a LiDAR point cloud with a temperature value attached to every point. There has been no publication using such a below canopy technology in a forest environment as far as we know. Therefore, we conducted a pre-study to prove the working principle and to gather first experiences with the technology. Therefore, we recorded a time series of transect walks through an

experimental forest plot on warm summer days with extensive instrumentations including sap-flux sensors on various trees, since we expected that evapotranspiration significantly influences the temperature regime within the stand (Ellsäßer et al., 2020). This study revealed remarkable insights since we discovered various effects which we did not expect to be visible in the data. Different bark structures could be visually determined due to the temperature difference between the inner and outer bark and we could show a temperature gradient along the boles created due to the cold groundwater uptake of the trees which was significantly related to the sap-flow. Additionally, we could show that the technology nicely depicts sun flecks due to a fast rise of the surface temperature (Frey et al., 2023a, 2023b).

Figure 2: Terrestrial LiDAR Point cloud of a single *Malus domestica* tree (a) classified as wood (brown) and leaf (green) points and (b) reconstructed polygons with simulated shade for 2 pm. The blue boxes highlight the magnified area of the point cloud (c) and the respective reconstructed polygons (d). Figure b and d were generated in Blender ray tracing software for visualization purposes.

We developed a technical solution to generate PAR values with a smaller temporal coverage but a larger spatial coverage. A mobile PAR measurement and position tracking system was developed based on low cost multispectral sensors (Comella et al., 2022) and a high quality differential global navigation satellite system (dGNSS, Reach M2, EMLID Budapest, Hungary) receiver stabilised by a gimbal (DJI RS3, SZ DJI Technology Co., Ltd, Shenzhen, China) on a backpack. The system tracks the incident PAR and its position and GPS-time simultaneously to perform transect walks through forest research sites and stores the result on an Arduino data logger (Feather M0 Adalogger, Adafruit Industries, LLC, New York, USA). Additionally, a second PAR sensor with logger is connected to the dGNSS base station with clear sky view. Therefore, we can compute the relative PAR at the rover.

We used this measurement setup to record TLS scans with RGB images on 12 research sites of 1 ha each, additional 5 TLS scans with Thermal images were conducted on every research site center. In tandem with the scans we recorded the PAR with our newly developed backpack system and at the dGNSS base station. The position of the scanner was also tracked with a dGNSS system operating with the same correction signal to achieve optimal spatial alignment.

To test our full pipeline we scanned the ICOS site at [Hartheim](#) in high detail with more than 100 single TLS scans under leaf on conditions. All scan position were registered, filtered (Reflectance > -15 dB, Pulse deviation < 15), combined and down sampled (1 pt/cm³) using RiScan Software (RIEGL Laser Measurement Systems GmbH, Horn, Austria). We used FSCT to classify wood and leaf points (Krisanski et al., 2021) and our R package CspStandSegmentation to segment single trees (Frey & Schindler, 2024b). We applied our species classification model on the single tree point clouds (Frey & Schindler, 2024c). For all species we generated a leaf optical reflectance and transmittance spectra within the PAR domain (400 – 700 nm) using the PROSPECT 4 model (Feret et al., 2008) within the implementation of the Rprospect R-package (Serbin, 2013) using gap filled average leaf trait data from the TRY database (Kattge et al., 2020; Mederer et al., under review). We utilized our mesh reconstruction model to generate a separate mesh model for leaf and wood for every tree and link it to the spectral properties according to the species (Frey & Kröner, 2024). We imported the geometries and spectra into LESS radiative transfer model (Qi et al., 2019) and generated first preliminary renderings of the canopy which shows promising detail (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Hartheim ICOS site seen from above with the tower at the top-left corner. Left: false coloured point cloud with lower points in blue and higher points in yellow. Right: example RGB rendering of the generated forest stand mesh model.

Overall the project has made significant progress at multiple methodological scientific frontiers. Together with our international partners we could contribute a state-of-the-art tree species classification based on TLS point clouds, we have contributed an important outlook about thermal-imaging and TLS sensor fusion and we have been able to prove the feasibility of leaf polygon reconstruction. Nevertheless, due to limitations in time and complications in the acquisition of field data during the pandemic we have not been able to fully cover our workplan and various subprojects are still in various stages of completion.

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4 Published Project Results

4.1 Publications with scientific quality assurance

Frey, J., Holter, P., Kinzinger, L., Schindler, Z., Morhart, C., Kolbe, S., et al. (2023) Detailed mapping of below canopy surface temperatures in forests reveals new perspectives on microclimatic processes. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 341, 109656. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2023.109656>

Frey J, Schindler Z, McClatchy P, Morhart C, Larysch E, Seifert T (2025) The 3D reconstruction of wood and leaves from terrestrial laser scanning – a case study on PAR measurements below a solitary *Malus domestica* tree. *Silva Fennica* 59. <https://doi.org/10.14214/sf.24027>

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4.2 Other publications and published results

Frey, J., & Kröner, K. (2024). JulFrey/dotshadow: Dotshadow - create a polygon reconstruction of vegetation from terrestrial LiDAR data for radiative transfer modelling (Version v0.1.0) [Computer software]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14204435>

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